

THE ROLE OF BORROWINGS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERLINGUAL COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

Borrowed words in languages are words that have passed from one language to another due to linguistic contact and have become part of the lexicon of that language. Borrowed words are one of the main ways of enriching the lexicon of the language, and there is no language in the world that has not received any borrowed words.

Introduction. To assimilate - to be accepted from a foreign language. Nowadays, there are a large number of words that have been assimilated in the Uzbek literary language. In linguistics, there is a concept similar to acquisition called code-switching. The main difference between code switching and acquisition is that it is possible to meet elements of two or more languages in one speech. The acquired form of a concept is embedded in the language it is learning and is known and understood by almost every representative of this language. Some words have been used in the language for thousands of years, and most people do not even notice that it is a foreign element.

Research methods. The sharp growth of communication in the language environment, the development of borrowings and the service sector, borrowed words, media, educational, advertising, exhibition projects require a special analysis of this phenomenon in the science of language. Borrowings is one of the popular types word composition which can be used as a type of communication, but its scientific study began relatively recently.

Results and discussions. Over the millennia of communicative practice, the value system, which is the basis of borrowed words, has fully manifested itself and has been well studied. An extensive system of words of borrowed words has developed - from oral tradition and sermon to an official speech at a dispute or an editorial in an illustrated magazine.

A rich vocabulary in any language indicates the level of intellectual development of a person. People with a rich vocabulary are considered smart, creative, more successful. Indeed, people with a rich vocabulary get a job faster, move up the career ladder more easily and successfully, and this can be fully attributed both to competence in this area in relation to their native language and to the foreign language being studied.

For example, the Chinese word putao (grape) comes from the old Iranian language more than two thousand years ago, and it is pronounced as bodda. Today, it is so ingrained in the Chinese language that no one, except a few linguists, notices that it is a foreign element. It is,

among other words, a regular Chinese word, in other words, it has been completely absorbed into the Chinese language.

The assimilation of the acquired word also has its own levels. It depends on the extent to which the acquired word matches the grammar, phonology and writing system of the acquired language. For example, most Japanese people know that the words vegetarian and baiorin are derived from the English words vegetarian and violin. Some Japanese even pronounce vegetarian and vaiorin by pronouncing the v sound, which does not exist in Japanese. Also, the fact that they have a foreign root is also known from the alphabet in which they are written, since these words, like other adopted words, are expressed in katakana, not in the more widely used hiragana alphabet. Even the Portuguese word pan (bread), which has been used in Japanese for centuries, is written in katakana to indicate that it is a foreign word. The words bejitarian and baiorin, let alone the word pan, have already become part of the Japanese lexicon. No one code-switches to Portuguese or English using these words.

As an example of grammar absorption, we can take the Latin word cacti, which also forms the plural in English, as an example. In addition, cactuses can be pluralized in English. We will analyze another example in the Swahili language. The Swahili language has adopted the Arabic word for book, and the English word club has also entered the language. The first syllable of these two words is interpreted as a prefix, ki-, and when forming the plural, this prefix is changed and in Swahili, kitabu kitab and vitabu books, kilabu club and vilabu clubs are formed. Even in Uzbek, many words borrowed from Arabic have changed to plural form, but now they are used as double words[2]. For example, the first element in a pair of words such as behavior and condition is the singular form of a noun in Arabic, and the second element is the plural form of the same noun in Arabic.

Borrowed words are mainly exchanged between a language recipient and a language donor. The language recipient is derived from the Latin word "receipt" and is considered a language that adds a specific word to its lexicon[3].

The language donor is derived from the Latin word donare, to give a gift, to make a sacrifice. For example, the word orangutan is translated from Malay to English and Uzbek as "man of the forest" ("orang" is a person, "utan" is a forest)[1]. In this situation, English and Uzbek languages are considered as recipient Malay language and donor language.

In general, any language can be both a donor and a recipient, and practically any language plays such a role. But in many cases it has been observed that the donor language is socially, culturally or politically superior to the recipient language.

English is probably the most common donor language today. Many Asian and African languages are now borrowing dozens, if not hundreds, of words from English. When a country is colonized by another country, local languages usually absorb elements of the language of the occupiers to a large extent. For example, the Vietnamese language borrowed elements from French, the Wolof language in Senegal borrowed elements from French, and the Gambian language borrowed elements from English. A similar situation occurred in the English spoken by common people in England, which was ruled by the French elite during the Middle Ages.

Another type of donor languages can be the languages of nations that once played a key role in creating a great culture. A large number of words borrowed from the Chinese language are

found in Japanese, Korean, Vietnamese and other East and Southeast Asian languages; similar words borrowed from the Arabic language can be found in large numbers in Urdu, Persian, Turkish, Swahili, Fulani and other languages of the Muslim world. Languages such as Urdu, Turkish and Uzbek have also adopted many words from Persian[4].

Sometimes, even dead languages can serve as donor languages. In the East, Sanskrit and Classical Chinese are practically no one's mother tongue, but they are still culturally used as sources for modern languages. The same process is carried out in the West in classical Greek and Latin. Modern Chinese uses classical Chinese and Indian uses Sanskrit to create new words not only for objects and concepts that existed in ancient times, but also for new concepts arising from new innovations. While Hindi borrows from Sanskrit, Urdu borrows from Arabic, and this very phenomenon is seen as one of the main criteria that separates the two languages. For example, the word dhanyavad, which is interpreted as a form of the Hindi word rahmat, is derived from Sanskrit, while the Urdu word shukriya is derived from Arabic. The assimilated elements of the recipient language that fill the lexical gap are called cultural appropriations. Such words enter the culture of the acquired language with a new object or concept. A good example of this is the words Japanese sushi Swahili safari which do not exist in many western languages.

On the other hand, appropriations that express a concept corresponding to an element already present in the recipient language are called root appropriations. An example is the Chinese phrase bai-bai, which is used instead of zai jian (goodbye). Root appropriations appear and are used as foreign elements in the code-switching of a new language, and are then adopted as a whole. Cultural appropriations are much more likely to be assimilated than native appropriations.

Conclusion

Thus, cross-linguistic communication produces the following results:

1. Interlingual communication enriches both the donor language and the recipient language;
2. As a result of mixing two languages, new languages are created (creole, pidgin, mixed languages);
3. The complete disappearance of a relatively weak language due to interlinguistic communication under the influence of the hegemonic language.

Nowadays, the process of extensive globalization leads to the acceleration of interlanguage communication, and serves to increase the influence of the hegemonic languages of the world, especially English, on other languages. Although interlanguage communication has been frequent and slow throughout human history, it has never stopped, and its role in the development of languages is immeasurable.

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